

CASE STUDY ANALYSIS :

THE MERGER BETWEEN PLANET LABS AND SPAC DMY TECHNOLOGY GROUP Inc IV

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1. Introduction

1.1. Company Description

Planet Labs, headquartered in San Francisco, California, is a company in the field of earth imaging and satellite technology (Planet, n.d.). The company was established, named Cosmogia, in 2010 by former NASA scientists Will Marshall, Robbie Schingler, and Chris Boshuizen. Today Planet Labs has emerged as a leader in providing high-resolution satellite imagery and data analytics for multiple applications (Leary, 2023).

The company provides products for planetary tasks, planetary variables, maps, and analytical feeds (Planet, n.d.). It contributes products and services to different industries, including civil government, agriculture, science programmes, energy and infrastructure, drought management, finance, forestry and land use, mapping, maritime, sustainability, planetary programmes at federal and non-profit levels. They try to create an understanding of our planet through continuous monitoring and analysis of its surface (Tim, 2022). The company operates the largest fleet of Earth-imaging satellites in orbit, known as Doves. The fleet consists of over more than 200 satellites. These small, agile satellites are equipped with imaging sensors capable of capturing detailed images of Earth's surface with clarity and precision. Besides the Doves, Planet Labs also manages another satellite constellation called SkySat (Planet, n.d.). This is a smaller constellation of 20 satellites that can image any point on Earth in high resolution. Planet Labs decided to provide limited open access to that information (Planet, n.d.). The company is situated in North America, Asia-Pacific, and Europe (Planet, n.d.). As we will discuss in the next section, The company went public via SPAC in late 2021, joining other aerospace companies who did the same (Planet, 2021).

In addition to its main activities, Planet Labs has developed data analytics tools and platforms together with other companies to extract extra insights Using machine learning algorithms and geospatial analysis techniques (Leary, 2023). The company can identify patterns, trends, and anomalies in the data, empowering customers to make data-driven decisions and gain a deeper understanding of complex Earth systems. Beyond those commercial applications, Planet Labs also contributes to scientific research (Planet, n.d.). The company collaborates with academic institutions, research organizations, and government agencies to support scientific studies.

Today, Planet Labs has over 600 full-time employees (Planet, n.d.). They currently serve more than 34,000 users, 700 customers, and 200 partners. In 2023 their revenue was \$191,3 million up 45,8% from the previous year. (Planet, n.d.)

1.2. Event Description

In July 2021, Planet Labs announced its intention to merge with SPAC DMY Technology Group Inc IV, marking a significant milestone in its growth journey by transitioning to a publicly traded company (Planet News, 2021). This move was finalized on December 7, 2021, when the merger was completed, and Planet Labs officially registered as a public benefit corporation (PBC), rebranding as Planet Labs

PBC (dMY Technology Group, 2023). This change to a PBC status highlighted the importance of funding, which was precisely the central point of this merger.

The merger with DMY Technology Inc valued Planet Labs at approximately \$2.8 billion, with around \$500 million in capital infusion (A Brief Overview of Planet Labs: Saving the Earth (for a Small Fee), n.d.). As a PBC, Planet Labs declared its mission to image the Earth daily, making change visible, accessible, and actionable for the betterment of humanity.

The merger was strategically focused on three key areas of investment: Firstly, strengthening the sales organization to expand market reach and drive business growth; secondly, establishing a global customer success organization to ensure customer satisfaction and retention; and lastly, investing in software development to empower customers with effective tools, ultimately reducing the need for extensive customer support and enhancing overall efficiency (Maurer & Maidenberg, 2023). These areas were identified as the primary goals of the merger, allowing Planet Labs to leverage its resources more effectively and achieve its mission of making a positive impact on society and the environment while ensuring financial success.

1.3. Case Study

Once a promising space stock with rapid growth potential, Planet Labs PBC boasted plans for significant expansion, boosted by its IPO in December 2021 and its impressive constellation of Earth observation satellites. However, along with the announcement of its merger, Planet Labs announced its commitment to sustainability and it led the company's stock to take a downturn. In the last three years, profit margins have declined, and guidance for future sales indicates further slowing growth (Smith, 2023).

This case study aims to dissect the business model of Planet Labs using Business Model Canvas and understand the effects of the merger on the company's growth. By comparing various categories of the business model canvas from before and after the event, we have attempted to evaluate the changes caused by the merger. Ultimately, we aim to dissect the complexities of aligning corporate objectives with broader societal concerns, offering insights into managing digital innovation within evolving corporate frameworks. When studying the case study, we expected more changes and stronger impact from the merger on the business model. However, you will see below that the crux of the company stayed the same. Although the merger led to a fall in stock price, it allowed the company to expand faster by injecting the much-needed cash. As most of its stockholders and analysts point out the company's cash burn issue, the management has been making active efforts to increase revenue and efficiency in its finances. Lastly, the company is still developing ways to inject its offerings into different industries by expanding the quality and quantity of its offerings, shaping a more promising future ahead.

1.4. Methodology

To analyze Planet's business using Osterwalder's Business Model Canvas (2010) as a framework, our methodology is centered on a comprehensive review of documents provided by Planet and other relevant

sources available on the internet. Specifically, we sought to address the effects of the merger on Planet's growth.

A qualitative approach was employed to analyze the content of the selected documents. Key themes, patterns, and insights related to the research objectives were identified through systematic reading and coding of the documents. To ensure the credibility and trustworthiness of the findings, our team independently reviewed a subset of documents and participated in discussions to reach consensus on coding and interpretation.

Furthermore, we employed rigorous criteria for document selection, focusing on materials directly related to Planet's business operations, industry analyses, and market trends. Documents were screened based on relevance, credibility, and recency. Findings from the document analysis were triangulated with existing literature and, where applicable, with other sources of data to enhance the validity and reliability of the conclusions drawn. This triangulation process involved comparing and contrasting findings from different sources to identify converging and diverging trends.

Steps taken in document selection, data collection, and analysis were transparently documented to facilitate replication and scrutiny by other researchers. Specifically, detailed records were kept regarding the source, date of publication, and format of each document.

2. Impact Analysis

2.1. Key Partners

As mentioned earlier, Planet Labs is a world leader in the field of Earth imaging and satellite technology (Planet, n.d.). Therefore, to remain continuously successful and also improve itself, the company is looking for partners to write a success story together. Key partners are indispensable assets for any company, serving as strategic allies that complement and enhance its capabilities (Dieffenbacher, 2024). Like any other company, the number of partnerships evolves as the company grows. At Planet Labs, for example, they were already working with NASA and other companies in 2015 (Niles, 2014). Gradually, the number of partnerships grew and in 2017, Planet Labs launched their partnership programme, named "Planet Orbit" (Planet, 2017). This programme still exists to this day.

The merger took place so that the company would grow in all its facets (Planet, 2021). So did the number of partnerships. According to their own website Planet Labs now has over more than 200 partners (Planet, n.d.). We can divide them in four different key partnerships: strategic partnerships, technology partnerships, research and academic partnerships, supply chain partnerships. First of all, **strategic partnerships** help them to explore new opportunities and stay competitive in the market. They have formed alliances with for example governments, space companies and other private companies. A key example of a strategic partnership is Google (Alamalhodaie, 2021). For example, Planet Labs customers can use Google Cloud to store their data. This is just one of many examples of how Google and Planet Labs work together. Secondly, **technology partnerships** help Planet Labs to develop and improve satellite imaging and data processing (Planet, n.d.). Further, **research and academic partnerships** allow Planet Labs to open up their knowledge in satellite technology and data analysis (Planet, n.d.). They try to contribute to scientific research projects but also at the same time try to gain new scientific knowledge to improve their services and improve the company. Therefore, they work closely with universities and other research institutions. Last but not least, Planet Labs also forms **supply chain partnerships** (Planet, n.d.). These partners help Planet Labs to develop their hardware and software. The most important resources they acquire from partners are diverse. For example satellite components and technology help Planet Labs to build and operate their satellites (Mason, 2023). On the other hand they also acquire data processing and analytics tools to process and analyze the data they generate (Planet, n.d.). From this data they try to gain new insights to create value-added products and services. Lastly, access to (new) markets and customers are obtained through partnerships with distribution channels (Planet, n.d.). They help the company to expand its market reach.

The three key suppliers they work together with are launch service providers, ground station network operators and also spacecraft component suppliers. **Launch service providers** are crucial for Planet Labs's satellites (Safyan, 2021). They launch them into orbit and monitor them to ensure reliable service from Planet Labs. **Ground station services** make sure there is communication between Planet Labs and their satellites (Longanbach, 2022). They ensure there is safe and constant data transmission to the company. **Spacecraft component suppliers** deliver products so that Planet Labs can build their satellites (Mason, 2023). Planet Lab needs for example antennas, sensors, thermal control systems and solar panels in order to build their satellites.

2.2. Key Activities

Key activities are the fundamental tasks a business takes to deliver value to its customers, determined more by intuition and identifying the necessary steps to provide value rather than relying only on market research. (Research Guides: Business Model Canvas). Planet Labs key activities are:

Satellite Manufacturing: Planet Labs creates and launches CubeSats, these are small satellites with imaging sensors and communication systems that capture and transmit images of Earth (Devaraj, K, 2019). With around 1700 images of every place on Earth, Planet provides a massive dataset for commercial and humanitarian purposes through a near-daily stream of satellite imagery (Planet Lab, n.d.).

Satellite Data Provision: Planet's pivotal task is in offering high-frequency satellite data globally, a task that significantly aids businesses, governments, researchers, and journalists in making informed decisions. This global reach is made possible by 200 dove satellites, which diligently image the entire Earth daily. (Planet Lab, n.d.). Planet's monitoring system plays a crucial role in disaster response, as demonstrated by timely support during flooding and natural disasters (Planet Lab, n.d.). For instance, Planet was able to provide real-time updates on widespread flooding in central Greece, empowering the government To assess situations and take necessary steps promptly (Planet Scope, 2023).

Organizing Events: Planet organizes events, such as 'On The Road 2023', serving as a platform for global leaders to unite, fostering a spirit of collaboration and innovation in the Asia-Pacific region. These discussions revolve around democratizing data, sustainability goals, and leveraging satellite technology for agriculture, supply chain sustainability, and disaster risk reduction (Fule, J, 2023).

Product offerings and launches: Introduces new solutions like Forest Carbon Diligence and disaster management tools to enhance global preparedness and recovery efforts. Planet Offers products such as Planet Hyperspectral suite, Planet monitoring, Planet tasking, Planet selecting base maps, and Planet analytical feeds, which deliver global coverage and efficient data solutions (Planet Lab, n.d.).

Mapping: Planet's satellite imagery is leveraged for mapping purposes to ensure that digital maps remain accurate and current despite changes to the environment or urban landscapes (Planet News, 2021).

Acquisitions and Partnerships: Planet does Strategic alliances with entities like Sinergise, Synthetic and SI Analytics to bolster Planet's Earth data platform, advancing AI and geospatial analytics. As a result, a partnership with SI Analytics, a South Korean startup utilizing AI-powered analytics to enhance satellite imagery resolution for abnormality detection, aims to launch a North Korea Dynamic BMOA Search Project to improve global risk management and reduce tensions in Asia (Planet, 2023).

Sustainability transformation: Planet offers that empower companies to monitor sustainability across their entire value chain in an integrated manner. The company collaborates with partners to transform data into actionable strategies, facilitating ESG reporting and greater transparency. Organizations and countries can leverage Planet data and partner products to document sustainable practices, assess product lifecycles, and gain near real-time insights to contribute to sustainability efforts. Key focuses include ensuring

deforestation-free commodities, building supply chain traceability, tracking methane emissions, and monitoring biodiversity hotspots and forest carbon investments (Planet Lab Sustainability, n.d.).

Planet Labs' activities before and after the IPO event have been the same, but going forward with the transaction, Planet Lab has plans to boost its growth by venturing into new and existing markets. Additionally, they intend to develop new software and data products and solutions that leverage machine-learning technology (Planet News, 2021). Prior to listing, the company secured over \$450 million in venture capital funding, including investments from Google, Threshold Ventures, and DCVC Management Co., allowing for significant expansion of its satellite fleet and technology improvements of existing products and activities (Maurer, M, 2021).

2.3. Value Propositions

Planet Lab brings value to its customers by providing high-resolution satellite imagery and data analytics that enable them to monitor changes on Earth's surface, track environmental trends, and make informed decisions for various applications likely mentioned before. This value is rooted in how easily accessible and frequently updated the data is, which empowers customers with insights that are visible, accessible, and actionable (Open Data Access) .

Through Planet Lab's platform processes, global, near-daily stream of satellite data are guaranteed into the workflows, enabling workers and partners to quickly respond to a fast-changing world.

Driving values:

- **High-Frequency, Global Coverage:** Monitor your world with the most up-to-date, global satellite data, captured daily.
- **Analysis-Ready Data:** Focus your investments on solving core problems with clean, consistent, and harmonized data.
- **Seamless Access & Integration:** Build applications and scale insights across your organization with modern APIs & cloud architectures.
- **Trusted Partner:** Realize value quickly with Planet's suite of professional services, exceptional customer support, and a global community of users (Planet Labs PBC Company Profile - Overview, n.d).
- **Sustainable, ethical and responsible data collection:** Planet Lab is dedicated to practicing sustainable and responsible methods for collecting data, prioritizing both environmental conservation and ethical data handling principles.

All in all, since the merger and becoming a PBC, Planet Lab intended to intensify its efforts towards sustainability. They emphasize their commitment to increasing global transparency and promoting greater understanding and care for the environment and wildlife (Planet Labs PBC ESG Report, 2023).

2.4. Customer Segments

In easy terms, customer segments are collections of potential buyers with similar needs and responses to marketing efforts, maximizing your value proposition (Figueroa, 2024). Planet Labs serves a niche market where diverse range of customers across various sectors, leveraging its high-frequency satellite imagery and data solutions to meet their specific needs (Gagliano, 2022). Niche markets are narrowly defined groups of consumers with specific characteristics. Unlike mass markets, they are smaller in number but more likely to purchase a particular product or service (Staff, 2024). From our research, we state that Planet labs customer segment has been similar before and after the merger event. The consumer segments are therefore distributed like this :

Government agencies: Governments use satellite data from Planet Labs for a variety of purposes, such as monitoring land, responding to disasters, planning infrastructure, and supporting defense and intelligence. By utilizing Planet's extensive global coverage and updates that are nearly real-time, governments can make informed decisions and improve public safety (Planet Customer Stories, n.d).

Commercial Enterprises: Many businesses across diverse industries, including agriculture, energy, infrastructure, forestry, insurance, and transportation, depend on Planet's satellite imagery for various purposes. They use it to monitor their assets, assess risks, gain market intelligence, optimize their supply chains, and evaluate the environmental impact of their operations. From keeping track of crop health to monitoring infrastructure development, commercial enterprises rely on Planet's data (Planet Customer Stories, n.d).

Research Institutions and Academia: Research institutions and academic organizations benefit from Planet's satellite imagery as it helps them conduct scientific research, monitor the environment, study climate change, analyse urban planning and ensure disaster resilience (Planet Customer Stories, n.d). Planet offers a program called Education and Research (E&R) that enables non-commercial research organizations to access PlanetScope and RapidEye imagery for research purposes. The program is open to users across 100 plus countries and over 1,000 universities, with more than 10,000 participants (Planet Science Programs, n.d).

Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs): NGOs can effectively utilize satellite data from Planet to support various humanitarian efforts, including disaster relief, conservation, and advocacy campaigns. By closely monitoring changes in land use, natural disasters, deforestation, and humanitarian crises, NGOs can more efficiently target their interventions, raise awareness, and provide support to vulnerable communities worldwide (Planet customer stories, n.d.).

Journalists and Media Outlets: Journalists and media outlets rely on Planet's satellite imagery to enhance their reporting and storytelling on various topics. These include environmental issues, human rights violations, geopolitical conflicts, and natural disasters. For instance, Following the announcement of airstrikes on Syria, Planet swiftly obtained before-and-after imagery of the Barzah research facility. Within an hour, the corrected imagery was distributed to journalists and analysts, aiding timely reporting on the event (Planet Stories, 2018).

2.5. Customer Relationship

Prior to Planet, specialized technical analysts manually processed outdated satellite data, often lagging by months. With Planet's automated interfaces, daily content is now delivered directly to customers' decision-support tools.

The company is dedicated to fostering strong customer relationships by providing easy access to critical geospatial data and analytics in a user-friendly format.

Community-based customer relationship: Planet Lab emphasizes on cultivating strong relationships with customers and potential customers at every stage of interaction. This involves actively and directly engaging with them to create positive experiences and foster lasting connections, this requires ongoing dedication and effort. Therefore, **feedback loops** are only natural; customers are provided with an online community forum and an active feedback loop to understand satisfaction and identify areas of improvement with their services.

Value-add customer relationship: Similar to the efforts of Planet Lab to foster a community-customer relationship based on loyalty, trust, and credibility. They also focus on personalized customer experiences. Rather than only aiming for brand loyalty, the focus is also on delivering **value** and meeting customer needs effectively. Prioritizing providing value and transparency, aiming to understand customer requirements and **educate** them on potential solutions.

Customer education: Planet Lab provides its customers with onboarding videos, in-depth guides, self-guided tutorials but also API documentation, developer tools, references, and tutorials to help them optimize the value they get from their services (Planet Labs PBC Company Profile - Overview, n.d).

To illustrate their commitment and loyalty towards their customers, Planet Lab highlights the appreciated relationship through numerous testimonials on their website. For example Louise Jones at McKenzie Intelligence Services emphasizes the assurance of data availability during disastrous events, enabling timely and effective response worldwide. Planet's unique revisit rate and global coverage ensure data capture even with no prior warning, aiding in assessing the impact of natural disasters quickly. This rapid response is crucial for aiding affected areas and informing insurance companies about potential financial implications (Planet Labs PBC Customer Stories, n.d). Since the creation of Planet Lab, trusted relationships with customers and partners have been at the center, after becoming public, their dedication towards society intensified even further (Planet Labs PBC ESG Report, 2023).

2.6. Key Resources

Here, we will analyze the different key resources and value proposition required before, during and after the merger for example distribution channels, customer relationships, revenue streams,... . Before the merger between Planet Labs and SPAC DMY, Planet Labs boasted a robust set of resources that propelled its operations forward in the space technology landscape. The company's original objective was to utilize space-gathered information to assist life on Earth. This is something they have done perfectly, so, as a result, they continued their momentum with their foundational key resources even after the merger with DMY. In

general, Planet Labs' key resources were strengthened, notably through easier access to funds and partnerships with the government and other companies.

Firstly, Planet Labs operates state-of-the-art **satellite constellations** equipped with advanced imaging technology (Planet, n.d.). These satellites provide valuable insights and services across various sectors, ranging from agriculture to environmental monitoring (Anul Haq, 2021). The three main constellations they own are Dove, RapidEye and SkySat with over 150 satellites in orbit (Planet, 2021). However, RapidEye is no longer in operation since March 2020.

In addition to satellite constellations, Planet Labs possess **sophisticated software systems** tailored for the efficient processing of satellite data. This capability is crucial for extracting valuable insights from the immense volumes of data generated by its satellite constellations. They use intern software but also external software. For example, Planet Labs has partnerships with Google so they can store data on Google Cloud. This includes the **data storage** which is a major tool for the company. Due to the massive volume of satellite imagery they capture daily, they require robust infrastructure for archiving and analysis, thus enabling them to deliver valuable insights and services to their customers. Through the merger, Planet Labs had the opportunity to expand their software mainly because they could raise more funds.

Another major key resource is simply the **daily Earth data** that they provide. This datas forms the foundation of their services and solutions, driving value creation for their customers and enabling various applications such as planet monitoring, planet basemaps, planet tasking, planet analytic feeds (Planet, 2019).

To support its satellite operations, Planet Labs strategically positioned **ground stations** worldwide to receive and process data (Longanbach, 2022). This infrastructure ensures seamless functionality and data transmission from satellites to end-users. In 2022, they had 48 ground stations across 11 countries.

Furthermore, concerning financial key ressource, Planet Labs had access to substantial **funding and investment**, facilitated by a network of investors and partners. This financial backing enabled the company to pursue ambitious initiatives and invest in cutting-edge technology. For example, in May 2015, Planet Labs raised a total amount of \$183 million in venture capital financing (Skybrokers, n.d). They also received funding when they acquired BlackBridge and its RapidEye constellation in July 2015 (Foust, 2023). This key resource has been effectively strengthened following the merger with DMY, giving them access to more funds and greater visibility to potential investors.

Therefore, **Strategic partnerships** also play a pivotal role in Planet Labs' success. Collaborations with governments for authorization and with industry giants like Google fostered synergies and expanded market reach, further solidifying Planet Labs' position in the space technology sector. These partnerships enable the company to access new opportunities and further solidify its position in the space technology sector. This point was strengthened after the merger due to a greater visibility on the market. For example, after the merger, in May 2022, they entered into a partnership with SES Government Solutions (Jewett & Jewett, 2023). The contract was valued at US\$28.96 million and awarded by NASA's Communications Services Project. The purpose was to develop and demonstrate near-Earth communication.

Concerning Human key resources, behind Planet Labs' technological prowess, is **a team of skilled engineers and expert workers** dedicated to driving innovation and maintaining operational excellence. Their expertise is instrumental in developing and maintaining the company's cutting-edge technology solutions.

Overall, post-merger, the combined entity continued to leverage Planet Labs' foundational resources, prioritizing strategic partnerships and collaborations to drive growth and innovation in the dynamic space technology landscape. This merger has greatly allowed Planet Lab to expand and evolve, which has made it possible to acquire complete recognition in the world of satellite imaging. However, from a concrete point of view focusing on key resources, there hasn't been a significant change except for the fact that they now have access to more funds.

2.7. Channels

The channels in a business model refer to the various ways through which a company reaches and interacts with its customers to deliver its value proposition. Channels play a crucial role in determining how customers discover, purchase, and receive products or services. Before the merger between Planet Labs and SPAC DMY, Planet Labs utilized a variety of channels to engage with customers and stakeholders and it didn't change so much after the merger they continued to leverage and expand upon the channels while potentially introducing new strategies.

The main channel is **Direct sales efforts**, which focus on clients such as farmers. For example, customers can directly ask for information and buy the products from the website or they can also subscribe to their program so the customers can get daily imagery and planetary data focused on areas of interest (Planet, n.d.). This is the only channel which changed a bit after the merger because they transitioned direct sales models to **subscription-based approaches**, particularly targeting agriculture companies for satellite imaging services.

Another channel is **collaborations** with governmental organizations and other companies providing opportunities for partnerships (Planet, n.d). After the merger, they strengthened ties with **governmental organizations**, especially in defense and emergency response sectors, and remained a priority to secure contracts and partnerships.

Online platforms and explorer tools play a crucial role in marketing, sales, and customer engagement, facilitating digital interactions and transactions (Planet, n.d.).

Strategic partnerships with other companies or organizations are instrumental in expanding market reach and enhancing offerings.

Additionally, **a network of resellers** distribute products and services, tapping into existing distribution channels and networks (Discounted cash flow, 2023). For example, Planet labs has partnered with integration software like ESRI and QGIS to provide customers with easier access to its data through a simplified interface.

Furthermore, Participation in **industry events and conferences** facilitate networking opportunities and technology showcases, while collaborations with academic and research institutions fuel innovation and technological advancements within Planet Labs (Planet, n.d.). **Collaboration with academic and research institutions** is also a pivotal key to drive ongoing innovation and technological advancements within the realm of Planet Labs' operations.

Finally, the **introduction of API and developer tools** facilitate integration and customization of satellite data, potentially opening up new revenue streams and partnerships (Planet, 2019).

Overall, the merger likely led to a strategic realignment of channels and resources within Planet Labs, enabling the combined entity to capitalize on synergies and better serve its customers and stakeholders in a rapidly evolving market landscape.

2.8. Cost Structure

The cost structure for Planet Labs PBC (PL) comprises essential components vital for business operations and growth. As the business remained the same, the cost structure did not undergo major changes after the merger, however, the company announced to broaden its reach by investing more in awareness and adding more industry verticals like forestry and finance. In his Keynote Speech, CEO Will Marshall also emphasis on its goal to benefit society at large by becoming a Public Benefit Company (PBC).

Satellite Manufacturing and Launch Costs: This is one of the significant costs for companies like Planet Labs. The cost includes designing, building, testing, and launching satellites into space.

Research & Development: PL heavily invests in R&D to enhance satellite technology and data processing capabilities. In 2023, R&D expenditure amounted to \$1,10,916,000 covering skilled personnel, equipment, and software acquisition (Planet Labs PBC, 2023).

Operations & Maintenance: Costs associated with satellite maintenance, ground station operation, and data processing centers are incurred. This encompasses material procurement, production facilities, and ongoing operational expenses.

Data Processing and Analysis: Another significant cost component is related to processing the raw satellite imagery data into usable information. This involves the development and maintenance of software algorithms, data analysis tools, and infrastructure for processing vast amounts of imagery data.

Marketing & Sales: Investment in marketing and sales activities like advertising, promotions, and sales commissions is crucial for customer acquisition and retention. In 2023, PL allocated \$78,020,000 for sales & marketing (Planet Labs PBC, 2023).

Infrastructure & Overhead: Fixed costs for corporate infrastructure maintenance, including office space, utilities, and administrative expenses, are incurred. Additionally, expenses related to legal, accounting, and professional services are accounted for.

Customer Support and Service: Resources are allocated to staff the customer support team and develop service processes to ensure high-quality customer support. These expenses are essential for fostering strong customer relationships and ensuring satisfaction.

2.9. Revenue Streams

Before the merger, the annual revenue for the company was \$95.74 million for the fiscal year 2020 and it grew by 18.21% in 2021 reaching \$113.17 million (Smith, 2023). Planet Labs generates revenue through various streams related to its satellite imaging and data analytics services. In 2021, its key revenue streams were from Civil (24%), Agriculture (23%), Defense (22%) and Mapping (17%) (Planet, 2021). Some of the key revenue streams for Planet Labs include dynamic pricing models tailored based on the client, they include:

Earth Observation Data Sales: Selling high-resolution satellite imagery and data to government agencies, commercial businesses, and non-profit organizations.

Subscription Services: Offering subscription-based access to its data and analytics platform for regular and ongoing data access.

Customized Solutions: Providing tailored solutions for specific customer needs, including specialized algorithms and applications.

Platform Licensing: Licensing its data and analytics platform to third-party organizations for integration into their products and services.

Value-added Services: Offering additional services such as data processing and analysis beyond raw satellite imagery.

API Access and Integration Services: Providing API access to its platform for integration into customers' software applications and systems.

Consulting and Professional Services: Offering consulting, training, and project-based services to optimize customer use of satellite imagery and data analytics.

Government Contracts and Grants: Generating revenue through contracts and funding from government agencies for satellite imagery and related services.

In fiscal year 2024, Planet Labs expects revenue to range from approximately \$248 million to \$268 million, with approximately 35% year-over-year growth at the midpoint. Although the stock is falling, the company is growing its revenue each passing year (Planet Labs PBC, 2024).

3. Company’s Response to Event

Figure 1

Planet Lab’s decision management timeline.

Note. The timeline showcases Planet Lab’s key management decisions leading up to the SPAC merger with dMY Technology Group and the chosen strategies that have preceded the merger. Overall business growth is witnessed. Own work.

Revenue Growth and Gross Margin Expansion:

Planet has shown a remarkable trajectory of revenue growth over the evaluated period. Starting with a revenue figure of \$131.1 million in 2022, the company witnessed a substantial soar to \$191.3 million in 2023, reflecting a noteworthy year-over-year increase of 46% (Planet Lab PBC, 2022). Projections for 2024 anticipate further growth, with revenue estimates ranging between approximately \$248 million to \$268 million, indicative of a projected growth rate of approximately 35% at the midpoint compared to 2023 (Planet Lab PBC, 2023). Concurrently, Planet's gross margins have shown a commendable expansion, evolving from 37% in 2022 to 49% in 2023. Projections for 2024 indicate sustained profitability, with anticipated gross margins between approximately 57% to 61% (Planet Lab PBC, 2024).

Looking ahead, Planet remains optimistic about its growth trajectory and financial performance (Planet, 2023). The projected revenue figures for fiscal year 2024 underscore the company's continued momentum and market demand for its offerings. With a steadfast focus on innovation, customer-centricity, and

operational excellence, Planet is poised to capitalize on emerging opportunities in the Earth observation market landscape, thereby driving sustainable long-term value for its stakeholders (Planet, 2023). However, concerns about Planet Labs' liquidity have been raised, as the company's cash reserves have decreased over the past year. In the previous quarter, the total cash and short-term investments went down to \$314.8 million from \$425.3 million a year ago, resulting in a \$110.5 million decline in twelve months (Financhill, 2024).

On August first 2023, Plane Lab's CEO Will Marshall announced "restructuring" as the reason for laying off 10% of its employees, about 117 individuals. Planet Labs operated with a lean approach historically but transitioned into a new operational mode after going public 18 months ago. This involved expanding teams and undertaking new projects to capitalize on market opportunities. While the business has grown rapidly, the expansion of projects has also heightened costs and complexities, resulting in some slowdowns. Additionally, changes in the macroeconomic environment have prompted the company to prioritize high-return opportunities to reinforce its path to profitability. This strategic shift aligns with previous communications regarding the company's financial goals (Planet, 2023).

Customer Relationships and Business Expansion:

Throughout the examined period, Planet has demonstrated a strong commitment to fostering customer relationships and expanding its market presence. The end-of-period (EoP) customer count experienced a notable increase, escalating from 607 customers in 2022 to 882 customers in 2023, denoting a 15% year-over-year growth (Planet Lab PBC, 2023). Currently, the company has 903 customers (Sheetz, 2021). Furthermore, the percentage of recurring annual contract value (ACV) reached a commendable 94% in the fourth quarter of 2023, underscoring the stability and predictability of revenue streams emanating from long-term customer commitments and subscription-based contracts (Planet Lab PBC, 2024.). Following the merger, the company changed its name to Planet Labs PBC. This signifies a shift in the company's identity and focus, aligning itself more closely with the operations and mission of Planet Labs Inc. Additionally, the company became a Delaware public benefit corporation (PBC). A PBC is a type of corporation that is intended to produce a public benefit and operate in a responsible and sustainable manner, balancing profit with broader social and environmental goals (Planet Lab PBC, 2021).

Strategic Initiatives and Technological Advancements:

Planet's strategic initiatives and technological advancements have been instrumental in driving business growth and differentiation. Notable highlights include strategic acquisitions, such as the integration of Salo Sciences and Holding Sinergise d.o.o., augmenting the company's technological capabilities and product offerings. This is Planet's sixth acquisition : BlackBridge group of companies in 2015, Terra Bella business from Google in 2017, Boundless Spatial, Inc. in 2019, VanderSat B.V. in 2021, and Salo Sciences, Inc. in 2023 (Business Wire, 2023).

Right after the merger Planet lab brought Niccolo de Masi director of dMY Technology Group, Inc. IV, on their Board of Directors alongside recent additions Ita Brennan and Vijaya Gadde, bringing more expertise in technology, operations, and public markets. Planet hired Niccolo de Masi because of his valuable experience in mergers and acquisitions, particularly with companies going public through SPACs and his track record of serving on the boards of public companies. His strategic value lies in his ability to

provide invaluable insight and expertise in navigating the complexities of taking a company public and managing the transition to a publicly traded entity (Planet, 2021).

Moreover, strategic collaborations with government agencies like the BKG, which is the German federal government (Satnews, 2022) or UAE Space Agency (Holmes, 2023) and commercial entities have fortified Planet's market position and facilitated the delivery of innovative solutions to address global challenges (Planet PBC, 2024.). In 2022 Planet's disclosed its largest (government) contract to date, a \$146 million award from the National Reconnaissance Office (NRO) for imagery services over five years. Unlike other companies, Planet revealed the initial commitment for the first five years but did not divulge the total potential value over 10 years. The contract nearly doubles Planet's backlog and signifies the NRO's confidence in Planet's capabilities (Werner, 2023). Planet also reported growing demand across various vertical markets and expects its revenue split between government and commercial sectors to remain consistent (Werner, 2023). Regarding commercial entities, the Integration of artificial intelligence (AI) has further enhanced the usability and applicability of Planet's products, exemplified by collaborations with AI startups like Synthetica (Business Wire, 2023).

At last, Planet Lab is making strategic investments since the SPAC in three key areas. Firstly, they are expanding their sales team to increase their presence and outreach to potential customers, believing that more salespeople will result in more business. Secondly, they are establishing a global customer success team to ensure that existing customers are satisfied and successful in using their products or services. Lastly, they are investing in software development to create better tools for their customers, aiming to reduce the need for customer success assistance by providing more user-friendly and effective solutions. However, according to CFO Ashley Johnson, the company's priority with their money is to achieve cash flow break-even. This means cutting down on marketing and hires. They aim to use their available cash to sustain the business and avoid dependency on financial markets, thus focusing on achieving profitability rather than solely relying on growth (Maurer, Maidenberg, 2023).

4. Theoretical lens from Guest Lectures

Theory of Network Effects (Agnieszka Radziwon - Standardization)

Network effects occur when the value of a product or service increases as more people use it. It says that the technology's benefits for an individual actor increase along with the number of others using the same technology (Weigmann et al., 2017). This phenomenon arises due to the interconnectedness and interdependency among users within a network. Essentially, the more users there are the more opportunities for interactions, exchanges, and benefits (Belleframme & Peitz, 2018). Network effects can manifest in various forms, such as direct network effects, where the value of a product increases for existing users as more users join (e.g., social media platforms), or indirect network effects, where the value increases due to complementary products or services (e.g., video game consoles and game titles).

In the context of Planet Labs, network effects play a pivotal role in shaping the company's growth trajectory and competitive position within the satellite imaging and data analytics industry. As Planet Labs expands its constellation of satellites and data sources orbiting the Earth, the value proposition of its services amplifies significantly. With an increasing number of satellites capturing imagery data from various vantage points and at different resolutions, Planet Labs can offer more comprehensive coverage and insights to its customers. This expanded coverage enhances the accuracy, frequency, and diversity of the data available, thereby making Planet Labs' offerings more valuable and appealing to customers across diverse sectors such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, urban planning, and disaster response.

Moreover, the accumulation of data over time not only improves the quality of insights but also enables the development of more sophisticated analytics and predictive models. Customers benefit from access to historical data, trend analysis, and predictive capabilities, further enhancing the utility and value of Planet Labs' services. Additionally, as Planet Labs' network grows, it can leverage economies of scale in data processing, storage, and distribution, driving down costs and potentially increasing profit margins.

As a result, the network effects generated by Planet Labs' expanding satellite constellation contribute to a reinforcing cycle of growth and competitive advantage. The company becomes increasingly entrenched within its ecosystem, attracting more customers, partners, and collaborators, thus solidifying its position as a leading provider of satellite imaging and data analytics solutions.

Theory of Lock-in (Mehdi Montakhabi - Business Models)

Lock-in, also known as customer captivity or switching costs, refers to a situation where customers become economically or psychologically bound to a particular product or service, making it difficult or costly for them to switch to alternatives (Roedenbeck & Nothnagel, 2008). Lock-in can arise due to various factors, including technological dependencies, network effects, contractual obligations, and customer preferences. Essentially, the more entrenched a customer becomes in using a particular product or service, the higher the barriers to switching to alternatives.

In satellite imaging and data analytics, given the specialized nature of Planet Labs' offerings and the investment required for customers to integrate and familiarize themselves with its platform, there exists a

potential for lock-in effects. Customers may become locked into using Planet Labs' services due to several factors:

Data compatibility: Once customers integrate Planet Labs' data into their workflows, systems, and applications, switching to alternative providers may require significant effort and resources to ensure compatibility with new data formats and processing methods. This compatibility lock-in can deter customers from exploring alternative solutions.

Familiarity: Customers who have become accustomed to Planet Labs' user interface, features, and functionalities may be reluctant to switch to unfamiliar platforms, even if comparable alternatives exist. The learning curve associated with adopting a new platform can act as a deterrent, reinforcing customer captivity.

The Cost of Switching: Beyond the financial investment in integrating new data sources and adjusting workflows, customers may incur opportunity costs associated with disruptions to their operations during the transition period. These switching costs can outweigh the perceived benefits of switching, leading customers to remain loyal to Planet Labs.

By investigating the extent of lock-in among its customer base, Planet Labs can gain valuable insights into customer retention dynamics and competitive positioning. Understanding the factors contributing to lock-in enables Planet Labs to devise strategies for enhancing customer satisfaction, mitigating churn, and reinforcing its competitive advantage in the satellite imaging and data analytics market.

Theory of Platform Strategies (Aline Muylaert - CitizenLab)

Platform strategies involve the creation and management of ecosystems that facilitate interactions and transactions among different stakeholders, typically mediated by a central platform. Platforms can take various forms, including social media platforms, e-commerce platforms, and more specialized industry platforms (Gawer, 2009). Key characteristics of successful platforms include openness, scalability, network effects, and the ability to generate and capture value from interactions among participants.

Although Planet Labs does not operate a traditional platform in the same vein as social media or e-commerce platforms, it employs platform strategies to facilitate interactions and transactions within its ecosystem of satellite operators, data users, and technology partners. Through its satellite constellation and data analytics platform, Planet Labs serves as a central hub, connecting various stakeholders in the satellite imaging and data analytics industry.

Planet Labs builds and leverages its ecosystem in several ways:

- By providing access to its satellite imagery and data analytics platform, Planet Labs enables data users to access and utilize valuable information for diverse applications such as agriculture monitoring, urban planning, and environmental assessment. This creates value for customers by offering insights derived from satellite data.
- Through partnerships with satellite operators and technology partners, Planet Labs expands its data sources, enhances its capabilities, and fosters innovation within its ecosystem. Collaborations with other

satellite operators allow Planet Labs to augment its constellation coverage and access additional data streams, further enriching its offerings.

- Planet Labs may also offer integration services and APIs, enabling third-party developers and organizations to build upon its platform and create complementary products and services. This openness fosters innovation and expands the range of solutions available within the ecosystem.

By exploring how Planet Labs builds and leverages its ecosystem, researchers and practitioners can gain insights into the dynamics of platform strategies in specialized industries. Analyzing the mechanisms through which Planet Labs delivers value to customers, fosters collaboration among stakeholders, and captures market share provides valuable lessons for understanding platform dynamics and ecosystem development in diverse contexts.

5. Forecast based on Case Study

According to Patrick Moorhead of Forbes, in 2021 Planet Labs was 5-7 years ahead of its competitors (Moorhead, 2021). Today in 2024, three years after the merger, the future still looks bright for the company. As mentioned earlier, the company's revenue is still growing and the number of Planet Labs' partners is also growing steadily (Planet, 2023). The company is a key player in the earth observation market thanks to its innovative approach to satellite imaging and data collection. However, standing still is going backwards in business, so in the following paragraphs we describe how we think Planet Labs can continue to improve itself and where there are opportunities.

Despite being the leader in its market, there is strong competitiveness in the satellite imaging industry and earth observation market (Leary, 2023). Companies like Spire Global, BlackSky, Maxar and Satellogic keep trying to sneak market share from Planet Labs. That is why Planet Labs is always looking for new markets it can enter with its products. New applications and uses for their products are emerging and therefore new markets. In the future, it could focus on new markets like the sports industry or event sector. Consequently, Planet Labs could establish new partnerships with companies active in these markets. This could also be a possible answer to their limited customer base. These partnerships are crucial to the ecosystem that Planet Labs has created through strategic collaborations with Google Cloud or Microsoft Azure, for example (Planet, 2024). Expanding strategic collaborations can strengthen the ecosystem to generate an even stronger "lock-in effect". This, in turn, can lead to a stronger and possibly larger market position.

Secondly, the world is changing fast. Therefore, with climate change, urban development, and global connectivity taking center stage, there's a growing need for reliable, real-time Earth observation data (Willige, 2024). Planet Labs finds itself strategically positioned to meet this increasing demand, making its timing ideal. As more industries adopt Planet Labs' solutions, a natural network effect occurs, boosting the value of their ecosystem. This could result in higher adoption rates and fosters innovation, strengthening their position in the market.

Data is growing exponentially, creating new opportunities for businesses to build service models around data and analytics. Revenue models must align with these value propositions (Schüritz et al., 2017). One business possibility could be for Planet Lab to sell its data to third parties for financial growth (Lotame, 2022). The company follows a subscription-based business model where customers pay for proprietary data feeds (Planet News, 2021). Some of Planet Labs' data can be sold to multiple businesses or companies. Planet Labs' data is included in the European Space Agency Third Party Mission Programme, making it available to the European research community, indicating that Planet Labs has established a mechanism for sharing its data with third parties, including both commercial and non-commercial entities, which opens a door for further income (Preston, S, 2022).

Any weakness can be turned into an opportunity. There are strict regulations in the satellite industry (ITU, 2022). Planet Labs is subject to heavy regulatory agreements from governments within which it operates. Indeed, to operate in space you need the right licenses. This can lead to delays or increased costs. With more and more governments starting to recognise Planet Labs' strong services, there is a possibility that

they could also change the regulatory framework within which Planet Labs has to operate. This could lead to new opportunities for Planet Labs to expand their products and services.

Lastly, the industry in which Planet Labs operates is characterized by continuous technological progress and improvement (StartUs Insights, 2024). The rise of AI and technological improvements to their satellites and software means that new uses and therefore new application possibilities can emerge. Think, for example, of increased resolution and accuracy that will ensure that Earth can be imaged even better. Improved satellites and software ensure that Planet labs can offer more value to their current clients and future customers. This can lead to higher sales and thus higher market share.

6. Anomalies & Insights

Anomalies

Planet Labs' business model diverges significantly from traditional satellite imaging approaches. Instead of selling high-resolution images to a select few, they deploy vast constellations of small, low-cost satellites to capture daily imagery of the entire Earth's landmass. Initially driven by a mission of open data accessibility, the company later shifted focus towards securing government contracts, notably with the Department of Defense (DoD), altering its trajectory.

This shift reflects broader industry dynamics, where government contracts, particularly from entities like the US military, wield considerable influence, steering industry priorities. Despite this, Planet Labs continues to collect a vast amount of data, offering it to subscribers through accessible, subscription-based services. This contrasts starkly with the conventional model, which tends to prioritize high-priced, high-resolution imagery on a per-image basis (Morrison, 2021).

By prioritizing accessibility and frequency over resolution, Planet Labs democratizes Earth observation data, catering to diverse sectors such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, urban planning, and disaster response (Gallagher, 2022). This innovative approach challenges industry norms and establishes Planet Labs as a significant player. However, it may face hurdles in persuading some customers of the value proposition of lower-resolution imagery compared to traditional alternatives.

Let's delve deeper into the anomaly in Planet Labs' business model:

Frequency over resolution: Traditional satellite imaging companies often prioritize high-resolution imagery, offering detailed views of specific locations but typically at a higher cost. Planet Labs, on the other hand, prioritizes frequency by capturing images of the entire Earth's landmass every day using its constellation of small satellites. While the resolution of individual images may be lower compared to high-resolution satellites, the ability to capture daily imagery provides valuable insights into dynamic processes and changes over time.

Subscription-based model: Instead of selling individual high-resolution images at a premium price, Planet Labs operates on a subscription-based model. This approach allows customers to access a continuous stream of imagery for a fixed fee, making it more affordable and predictable for a wide range of users, including researchers, government agencies, NGOs, and commercial businesses.

Democratizing access to data: By offering frequent and affordable access to satellite imagery, Planet Labs is democratizing access to Earth observation data. This has significant implications for various industries and applications, such as agriculture, forestry, urban planning, disaster response, and environmental monitoring. Small and medium-sized enterprises, as well as organizations in developing countries, can now leverage satellite imagery for decision-making and analysis without the high barrier to entry associated with traditional satellite providers.

Data-driven insights: Planet Labs not only provides raw imagery but also offers analytics and insights derived from its data. By combining satellite imagery with machine learning algorithms and geospatial analytics, customers can gain valuable insights into trends, patterns, and changes in the environment. This added value enhances the utility of Planet Labs' services beyond just providing raw data, making it a more attractive option for a diverse range of users.

Overall, the anomaly in Planet Labs' business model lies in its disruptive approach to satellite imaging, prioritizing frequency and accessibility over traditional high-resolution imagery. By leveraging technology innovation and a subscription-based model, Planet Labs has transformed the satellite imaging industry and opened up new opportunities for data-driven decision-making and analysis across various sectors.

Insights

The insights can reflect the potential opportunities and strategic advantages that the merger between Planet Labs and the SPAC DMY Technology Group in 2021 may have provided for the combined entity, as they are positioning as a pillar in the Earth observation and satellite imaging industry. This merger was a pivotal key point to continue growth and success.

Here, the main insight is the financial statements. Planet Labs has benefited from **access to additional capital raised** through this merger, allowing the company **to accelerate its growth initiatives, expand its satellite constellation, and invest in research and development**. With the easier access to funds, Planet Labs has accelerated their research and innovation in satellite technology, data analytics, and machine learning, leading to the development of new products, services, and solutions to address emerging market demands.

Planet also acquired a greater visibility and exposure in the financial market, potentially attracting more investor interest and facilitating future fundraising activities. Additionally, they could expand into new markets and reach a broader range of customers.

This merger enabled Planet Labs to establish **strategic partnerships** and **collaborations** with other companies in the technology and aerospace sectors, especially the combined expertise and resources of SPAC DMY to pursue new business opportunities or joint ventures. A key point is that Planet Labs has a **strong ecosystem** with strategic partnership especially with Google, for example. With such a partner by its side, Planet has the opportunities to improve their technology and store its data within one of the leading cloud platforms, Google Cloud.

In comparison to their competitors, Planet Lab stands as the undisputed leader in the satellite imaging field, boasting a robust ecosystem that outshines its competitors (Leary, 2023). The size of Planet Lab's constellation surpasses, making it the primary reason why companies like BlackSky or Satelloic are unable to rival. Moreover, Planet Lab's subscription program offers unparalleled added value that other companies like Maxar Company can not offer. Maxar, for example, still juggles with hundreds of contracts.

By studying Planet Labs' case, other companies can learn the significance of customer growth with financial performance to uphold investor confidence. Moreover, investing strategically in marketing can aid in reducing financial challenges and backing business objectives. Using current resources, like data assets, and exploring new market opportunities, such as satellite internet services, can stimulate future growth and diversify revenue.

It is for those reasons that Planet labs is at the top of the scale and is strongly inked in the market. From this derives the value of loyalty and trust towards their audience.

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